

PERCEPTION OF THE UNIVERSITY OF IBADAN NON-TEACHING STAFF TO KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND UTILIZATION OF ICT FOR ADMINISTRATIVE EFFECTIVENESS

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Abstract

Administrative Effectiveness (AE) is the level to which Non-Teaching Staff (NTS) discharge their administrative duties (security, library, maintenance, legal, medical, cleaning, planning and financial services, among others) in a way to complement the efforts of academic staff in the university. Reports showed that some NTS have been accused of poor performance as revealed in their lateness to work, absenteeism, indiscipline, and their poor manner of handling official matters among others. Such behaviour could lead to administrative ineffectiveness. However, past studies on AE mainly considered the use of ICT, time management, lecturers' perception of ICT integration, ICT adoption and attitude of lecturers rather than knowledge, attitude, or perceptions on ICT utilization. Given the lacuna identified, this study investigated the perception of the University of Ibadan (UI) NTS to knowledge, attitude and Utilization of ICT (UICT) for AE. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design with a population of 1020 NTS from 17 faculties in the UI. A purposive sampling technique was used to select five faculties in the UI. These faculties were selected due to the duration their students spend on a degree programme. The proportion-to-size sampling technique was applied to select 50% of NTS from each faculty (Arts-21, Education-48, Science-83, Social Science-21 and Economics-8), giving the study 181 respondents. A research instrument titled AE Questionnaire (AEQ) and Perception, Attitude, Knowledge and UICT Questionnaire (PAKUICTQ) with a reliability value of $r=0.78$ and 0.81 . Pearson Product Moment Correlation and regression analysis were used to test three hypotheses formulated in the study. The findings showed that there were significant relationships among perception, attitude and knowledge of UICT and AE among NTS in the UI. The results also revealed that attitude, knowledge and perception of UICT made relative and joint contributions to the AE in the UI. Based on the findings, the management of the university should continue to improve the administrative effectiveness of staff by changing the attitude and perception of non-teaching staff. There is a need for non-teaching staff to be continually trained on the acquisition of ICT skills.

Keyword: Perception, Knowledge, Attitude, ICT Utilization, Administrative Effectiveness

Introduction

Administrative effectiveness is the extent to which university non-teaching discharge their administrative duties to complement the effort of academic staff in the area of research, teaching and community service. Eden (2012) states that

administrative effectiveness involves planning, coordinating, controlling and commanding activities aimed at the fulfillment of the goals of a particular institution. The extent to which the goals are achieved depends greatly on the administrative effectiveness of the

organisation (university inclusive). Optimal administrative effectiveness of many NTS is not attained in many Nigerian universities and this has been one of the major concerns of stakeholders in the education sector (Abiodun-Oyebanji, 2020). The government of Nigeria employs the service of NTS to stir and manage the affairs of the university, these NTSs are expected to be in charge of administration. These NTS are administrative staff whose task is not to lecture but to assist academic staff in the university. The level of their performance determines how effective they are in attaining the university goal. It appears as if the effectiveness of NTS in universities of Nigeria is being questioned as manifested by the poor way and manner they perform their duties. Abiodun-Oyebanji and (2020) reported that some administrative personnel in the university system have been accused of poor performance as revealed by their lateness to work, absenteeism, indiscipline, poor leadership style, poor manner of handling official matters, poor time management among others.

It is, therefore, the function of NTS of any university to rest on the effectiveness of administrators. The ineffectiveness of NTS in the security services, library services, administrative services, maintenance services, legal services, medical services, cleaning services, planning services, and financial services may lead to low NTS productivity which invariably leads to low university goal attainment. Conversely, if NTS is performing these services as expected in the University of Ibadan, there would be a higher level of administrative effectiveness and goal attainment of the university (Iwuoha, 2018). Take for instance, the NTS of the University of Ibadan is expected to provide quality internet services for academic staff and students for effective teaching and learning while exams and records unit are expected to prepare

academic transcripts and issue results for students who have graduated in the system. Also, NTS who are in charge of the security unit on the campus are expected to patrol and ensure that the lives and properties of staff and students are protected and secured. Many of these units identified did not perform their statutory responsibility as expected. This in turn can affect the administrative effectiveness of NTS, and the missions and vision of the University if not addressed by stakeholders in the university. Comfort (2012) revealed that institutions with high levels of administrative effectiveness manifest a high level of discipline.

The NTS as administrators require human and material resources to be effective and efficient in record keeping and service delivery. The administrators of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) are expected to be efficient and effective in managing students' admission and school fees portals, transcripts, registration, examination, and graduation, among others. It seems that all identified duties of the ICT unit are not properly managed and this could create retrieval problems for administrative operations. The introduction of ICT into the administration and management of the university has helped to improve the administrative effectiveness of NTS. Most of the NTS largely depend on ICT to be able to perform well in the university environment (Ogunode, Babayo, Jegede and Abubakar, 2021). It is believed that well-processed and appropriately utilized ICT would facilitate the process of effective administration of NTS. When NTS in the universities find it difficult to utilize ICT to keep their records up to date and render their service as expected, this could stand as an impediment to administrative effectiveness (Yekini, Oloyede and Akinwole, 2020).

The utilisation of ICT involves using the available technologies to aid NTS

in discharging their administrative duties in the areas of security, library, maintenance, legal, medical, cleaning, planning and financial services in a way to complement the efforts of academic staff in the university. The utilisation of ICT in various offices of non-teaching staff is expected to facilitate effective administration. Soetan and Coker (2018) reported that a low level of utilizing ICT facilities by NTS would lead to ineffective administration. This suggests that poor utilisation of ICT like ICT gadgets; internet, computers, printers and cable would improve administrative effectiveness in Nigerian universities. Ufuophu and Ayobami (2012) observed that ICT, including internet, satellite, cable transmission and computer-assisted equipment are facilities, tools, or resources that could be used to process, store, preserve, access, retrieve and disseminate information with ease.

The attitude of NTS towards ICT usage is another variable in this study and seems to influence the administrative effectiveness of NTS at the University of Ibadan. Littlejohn (2002) described attitude as an accumulation of information about an object, person, and situation or experience, a disposition to act positively or negatively toward some objects. According to Williams and Iruloh, (2014), if the attitude of a person toward a given object is known, it could be used in conjunction with other situational variables to predict and explain the reactions of these individuals towards that object. Some NTS have positive attitudes toward the usage of ICT while some may have negative attitudes towards ICT usage. The attitude of NTS toward their perception of ICT seems to be negative and has become a matter of concern (Oyedeji, 2018). The researcher added that despite the huge advantages associated with ICT, most staff seem to spend more time at work on Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, Telegram, and Zoom to the detriment of the university's goals.

The ability of NTS to use ICT for effective administration depends on their attitude, knowledge, and perception towards ICT generally.

It is assumed that a positive attitude toward ICT by NTS may contribute to administrative effectiveness while a negative attitude could lead to ineffectiveness of administration. To some, attitudes toward ICT usage could be good, poor, positive and negative in their intensities or directions (Williams and Iruloh, 2014). The administrative effectiveness in the area of ICT has been put in doubt due to the poor attitudes manifested by some of the non-teaching staff at the University of Ibadan who appear to be non-committed to administrative effectiveness. The attitude of NTS towards ICT usage may influence administrative effectiveness. Because of this, the positive attitude of non-teaching staff towards ICT is crucial if a university wants a technological transformation that would allow innovation and administration effectiveness (Maker, 2020).

Knowledge of ICT usage is another element that appears to influence administrative effectiveness in the area of record keeping and essential services like security services, library services, administrative services, maintenance services, legal services, medical services, and cleaning services at the University of Ibadan. Knowledge ICT as used in this study refers to the ability of the university's non-teaching staff to use various ICT tools such as e-mail, the internet, the World Wide Web, intranets, extranets, online databases and other networking technologies for effective administration. Successful incorporation of ICT in the university education system relies heavily on the knowledge of non-teaching staff towards the usage of modern technologies for effective administration (Kpolovie, 2014). However, experience and skills are subsumed in knowledge of ICT usage

acquired by the non-teaching staff. Thus, experienced NTSs need to be confident in using ICT effectively in the documentation of administrative records (Kpolovie and Awusaku, 2016).

Knowledge of ICT usage encompasses understanding and applying a range of computer programmes, software and other applications. These applications include word processing, spreadsheets, databases, power points and search engines. All these applications are expected to be employed by NTS when preparing memos, computing students' results, transcripts, files and staff files, among others. The ability to manage all these applications requires knowledge if administrative effectiveness is to be achieved. Ogunode, Babayo, Jegede and Abubakar (2021) observed that an ICT-driven system takes care of keeping a mountain of files in offices as information and they can be processed, stored, and retrieved within the university if the systems are networked.

Perception of ICT usage may also influence administrative effectiveness among NTS in the University of Ibadan. Perception could also be defined as how something is regarded, understood, or interpreted (Oxford University Press, 2017). In other words, it is the impression or attitude grounded on what is thought or observed. The NTS adopts ICT in their various roles and responsibilities mainly because of its perceived benefits and importance to their output. Therefore, their perception of the usage of ICT for administrative effectiveness is very vital to its adoption. The perceived benefits may not only be personal to them alone but also to overall administrative duties in the university. ICT is perceived to have many advantages in achieving administrative effectiveness (Michael, Caroyline and Peter, 2019). Understanding their perceptions of the use of ICT is vital in determining the pace at which ICT policies

are implemented in the university administration.

It is therefore, for non-teaching staff in the University of Ibadan to carry out their administrative duties efficiently and effectively, especially in this age of knowledge-based technology and globalization, the use of ICT becomes imperative. There is a need for NTS to develop a positive attitude, adequate knowledge, good perception and utilization of ICT if administrative effectiveness is to be achieved. However, studies like (Abiodun-Oyebanji, and Omojola, 2020; Ajah, 2019; Birgit and Mario, 2017; Adetimirin, 2016; Mewcha and Ayele, 2015) have been conducted on the administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff, most of these studies focused on time management, the use of ICT, teachers' attitudes, female lecturers' perception of ICT Integration, ICT adoption attitude of lecturers and assessing teachers' perception with little or no focus on the combined influence of knowledge, attitude and perception of ICT usage on administrative effectiveness of NTS. It is against this background that the study investigated the perception of the University of Ibadan NTS to knowledge, attitude and utilization of ICT for administrative effectiveness.

Statement of the Problem

The report showed that some NTSs have been accused of poor performance as is revealed in their lateness to work, absenteeism, indiscipline, poor manner of handling official matters, poor leadership style, poor usage of ICT tools, the lack of proper management of students and staff record as well as ineffective services rendered in the institution. Such behaviour could lead to administrative ineffectiveness.

Some of these NTSs also appear not to have adequate knowledge that would aid the application of ICT skills to enhance

security services, library services, administrative services, maintenance services, legal services, medical services, and cleaning services, among others. The seemingly lackadaisical attitude and poor perception of ICT usage equally appear to be hampering the chances of achieving administrative effectiveness in the University of Ibadan. Past studies conducted on administrative effectiveness considered the use of ICT, teachers' attitudes and female lecturers' perception of ICT Integration rather than attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage. It is based on these scenarios that this study investigated the influence of the perception of the University of Ibadan non-teaching staff on knowledge, attitude and utilization of ICT for administrative effectiveness.

Purpose of the Study

Generally, the study investigated the perception of the University of Ibadan NTS to knowledge, attitude and utilization of ICT for administrative effectiveness. Specifically, the study examined the level of administrative effectiveness among non-teaching staff and investigated attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage among NTS in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Research Question

The following question was raised in the study

1. What is the level of administrative effectiveness among NTS in the University of Ibadan?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated:

H01: There is no relative contribution of attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage to administrative effectiveness among NTS in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

H02: There is no joint contribution of attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage to administrative effectiveness among NTS in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Methodology

The descriptive survey research design was employed for this study. The population of this study comprised 1020 NTS in 17 faculties in the UI. The sample size for this consisted of 181 NTS in the UI. The multistage sampling procedure was adopted for sample selection. A purposive sampling technique was used to select five faculties (Arts-42, Education-96, Science-166, Social Science-42 and Economics-16) in the UI. These faculties were selected due to the duration their students spend on a degree programme. Again, the proportionate-to-size sampling technique was applied to select 50% of NTS from each faculty (Arts-21, Education-48, Science-83, Social Science-21 and Economics-8) which gave the study 181 respondents. A research instrument titled AE Questionnaire (AEQ) and Perception, Attitude, Knowledge and UICT Questionnaire (PAKUICTQ) with a reliability value of $r= 0.78$ and 0.81 was used to elicit responses. The instrument was face and content validated by experts in the Department of Educational Management of the UI.

The questionnaire had three sections- A to C. Section A comprised items that seek demographic information about the respondents such as name of faculty, sex, age, and administrative experience among others. Section B considered attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage with three subscales- Attitude of ICT usage scale had 7 items; perception of ICT usage scale had 7 items with a 4-point Likert scale of Very High (VH), High (H), Low (L) and Very Low (VL) while knowledge of ICT usage scale has 10 items. Information levels about

knowledge of ICT usage among non-teaching staff were rated through I can use it to a small extent =1, I can use it satisfactorily=2, I can use it well =3 and I can use it very well. Section C focused on the Administrative Effectiveness Scale (AES) with ten items. Response anchor based on the four Likert points which range from Very Effective (VE); Effective (E); Minimally Effective (ME); Ineffective (I).

Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research question while inferential statistics of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) and multiple regression were employed to test hypotheses.

Result of the Findings

Research Question 1: What is the level of administrative effectiveness among non-teaching staff in the University of Ibadan?

Table 1: Level of Administrative Effectiveness

S/N	Statements	VE	E	ME	I	MEAN (\bar{x})	Std D
1.	Record keeping	69 (40.1)	62 (36.0)	23 (13.4)	18 (10.5)	3.06	0.98
2.	Online processing of academic transcript	50 (29.1)	84 (48.8)	14 (8.1)	24 (14.0)	2.93	0.97
3.	Computation of students result	70 (40.7)	63 (36.6)	16 (9.3)	23 (13.4)	3.05	1.01
4.	Registration of new students	51 (29.7)	65 (37.8)	33 (19.2)	23 (13.4)	2.85	0.99
5.	Maintaining discipline records of students	70 (40.7)	60 (34.9)	17 (9.9)	25 (14.5)	3.02	1.05
6	Internet facilities	57 (33.1)	62 (36.0)	27 (15.7)	26 (15.1)	2.87	1.04
7	Monitoring students' academic progress	56 (32.6)	59 (34.3)	34 (19.8)	23 (13.4)	2.86	1.02
8	Student portal	38 (22.1)	80 (46.5)	29 (16.9)	25 (14.5)	2.76	0.96
9	Speedy execution of tasks	38 (22.1)	80 (46.9)	29 (16.9)	25 (14.5)	2.72	1.06
10	Staff portal	51 (29.7)	84 (48.8)	19 (11.0)	18 (10.5)	2.98	0.91

Very Effective (VE); Effective (E); Minimally Effective (ME); Ineffective (I)

Table 1 reveals that 76.1% of the respondents had a high degree view that record keeping was effective (=3.06); 77.9% of the respondents thought that online processing of academic transcripts was effective (=2.93); 77.3% of the respondents confirmed that computation of

students result was effective (=2.85); 67.5% of the respondents maintained that registration of new students was very effective (=2.85); 75.6% of the respondents had high degree view that maintaining discipline records of students was effective (=3.02); 69.1% of the respondents

maintained that internet facilities was effective ($=2.87$); 66.9% of the respondents thought that monitoring students' academic progress was effective ($=2.86$); 68.6% of the respondents agreed that student portal was effective ($=2.76$); 69.0% of the respondents confirmed that speedy execution of tasks was very effective ($=2.72$) While 78.5% of the respondents had high degree view that staff portal ($=2.98$). Based on the result from the above table, the data indicates that the mean ratings of the respondents for items 1 to 10 are 3.06, 3.93, 3.05, 2.85, 3.02, 2.87, 2.86, 2.76, 2.72 and 2.98 with a corresponding standard deviation of 0.98, 0.97, 1.01, 0.99, 1.05, 1.04, 1.02, 0.96, 1.06 and 0.91. The cluster mean of the above items was accepted as all rated above the decision benchmark of 2.50 which shows that the level of administrative

effectiveness among non-teaching staff at the University of Ibadan was highly effective. This finding implies that the non-teaching staff of the University are highly performing their officer duties as expected. The finding of this study is tantamount to the result of Comfort (2012) who revealed that schools with high levels of administrative effectiveness manifest high levels of discipline. The finding of this study is against the finding of Abiodun-Oyebanji (2020) who reported that the level of administrative effectiveness of non-teaching staff was moderate.

Hypothesis 1: There is no relative contribution of attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage to administrative effectiveness among non-teaching staff in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Table 1: Attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage to administrative effectiveness

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients Beta	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
(Constant)	3.217	1.182		2.721	.007
Attitude of ICT usage	.485	.104	.453	4.669	.000
knowledge of ICT usage	-.159	.079	-.166	-2.010	.046
perception of ICT usage	.523	.101	.484	5.204	.000

a. Dependent Variable:

Administrative Effectiveness

The results in Table 1 indicated that with all the independent variables (attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage) individually entered into the regression model at once, Attitude of ICT usage relatively contributed 45.3%, knowledge of ICT usage relatively contributed 16.6% and perception of ICT usage relatively contributed 48.4 to the total variation in the administrative effectiveness. The table also revealed that only perception of ICT usage had the highest and most significant contribution to administrative effectiveness in the University of Ibadan (45.3%, $P < 0.05$). This implies that the attitude of ICT

usage is a potential predictor of administrative effectiveness. Therefore, the hypothesis for attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage to administrative effectiveness was rejected. Attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage make a significant contribution to the administrative effectiveness in the University of Ibadan. This finding agrees with the finding of Nwangwu, Ememe and Obike (2013) who investigated management information systems as a tool in the administration of secondary schools in Aba Education Zone, South East Nigeria. Findings showed that result-oriented administration and speedy execution of tasks constituted the general administrative

performance of secondary school principals.
Hypothesis 2: There is no joint contribution of attitude, knowledge and perception of

ICT usage to administrative effectiveness among non-teaching staff in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

Table 2: Joint Contribution and Administrative Effectiveness

REGRESSION	ANOVA ^a				
Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
R = .770	3002.978	3	1000.993	81.042	.000 ^b
R Square = .593	2062.706	167	12.352		
Adjusted R Square = .585	5065.684	170			

a. Dependent Variable: Administrative Effectiveness

b. Predictors: (Constant), attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage

The results in Table 2 showed that with all the predictor variables (attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage) entered into the regression model at once, there was a significant prediction of administrative effectiveness (R = .770; R² = .593; F value) = 81.042; p < .05). This showed that the independent variables accounted for 59.3% of the variance in administrative effectiveness. The remaining 40.7% might be captured by other exogenous variables that were not captured in the model. Based on this analysis, hypothesis 2 which states that there is no significant joint contribution of attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage to administrative effectiveness among non-teaching staff in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria was therefore rejected. This indicates that there is a significant joint contribution of attitude, knowledge and perception of ICT usage to administrative effectiveness among Non-teaching staff in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria The finding is similar to the finding of supports the findings of Al-Gharaibeh and Malkawi (2013) who conducted study on the impact of management information systems on the performance of governmental organizations and found that there was a significant impact of networks, individuals and procedures, and management

information system as a whole on the performance of governmental organizations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The university management should continue to improve on effectiveness of administrative staff by providing an enabling conducive environment. Management of the institutions should engage administrative staff, most especially those in the ICT section of the university to train and re-train non-teaching staff on how to use ICT in their respective career for effective administration.
2. Information and Communication Technology should be the modern means of improving administrative effectiveness, especially in the University system.
3. University management should encourage non-teaching staff to have a positive attitude toward ICT usage and perception of ICT usage to achieve administrative effectiveness in the university.

Conclusion

From the data collected and analysed in this study, it can be concluded

that there is a high level of administrative effectiveness among non-teaching staff at the University of Ibadan. This implies that non-teaching staff are effective in performing their administrative duties. In the same vein, the study established that the perception of ICT usage had the highest and most significant contribution to administrative effectiveness in the University of Ibadan. This implies that attitude toward ICT usage is a major factor that contributes to administrative effectiveness. It is equally established that a positive attitude, high knowledge and good perception of ICT usage improve administrative effectiveness among non-teaching staff in the University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

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